

The Socio-Economic Impact of the Samruddhi Expressway on the Villages of Vaijapur Tehsil: A Study of Utilization of Land Acquisition Monetary Returns

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Abstract:- Acquisition of land by a project usually causes loss of land and displacement of habitations warranting rehabilitation of people. But in the present case, the project does not cause dislocation of habitations leading to rehabilitation of people. Prior to the acquisition, the farmers had just enough income to meet the daily needs. So they had very little surplus money and hence they led a miserable life for decades. But after having received the money following type of changes have taken place in the lives of the farmers. The farmers have become self-employment by opening restaurants, on the state highway, the poultry business, grocery shops while others have bought commercial vehicle like trucks, Lorries, JCBs, tractors, pickup vans, goods carriers etc. Many farmers utilized the money for developing their land by digging wells, bore wells, constructing new farms lakes, laying pipelines etc. and some have bought bullock too. Large reservoirs have been created at the site excavated for secondary minerals along the Samrudhi expressway. The Samrudhi expressway has caused a great deal of damage to the environment due to the extraction of secondary minerals in the area. It has a protective wall on both sides has hampered the free movement of wildlife. There was a slight increase in the addiction level in these villages. There is a rise in consumption too. Similarly, people are fighting over the distribution of the money. This newly rising rich people in the village has started to lead the village in political matters. If the project is completed, it would be contribute in economy development, fast transportation, reducing journey time and road accidents, improving quality of life of the people/users by providing better, quick and safe commuting.

Keywords:- commercial property, employment, modernization, agriculture, family dispute.

I. INTRODUCTION

Transport is a basic infrastructural requirement for economic development community or country. It links the factor suppliers, producers and consumers. The ‘Mumbai-Nagpur Super Communication Expressway’ officially known as ‘Hindu Hrudaysamarat Balasaheb Thackeray Maharashtra Samruddhi Mahamarg,’ (HHBTMSM). The length of this six-lane highway is 710 km, width 22.5 M and height 4-12 M. This highway could be drives at a maximum speed of 120 km ph. Therefore, it will reduce the travel time between Mumbai and Nagpur by 8 hours (Eight hours instead of 16). This expressway traverse through 10 key districts directly include, Nagpur-Wardha-Amravati-Washim-Buldhana-Jalna-Aurangabad-Nashik-Ahmednagar-Thane. And indirectly 14 districts namely, Chandrapur, Bhandara, Gondia, Gadchiroli, Yavatmal, Akola, Hingoli, Parbhani, Nanded, Beed, Dhule, Jalgaon, Palghar and Raigad via feeder roads. The project is led by the Maharashtra State Road Development Corporation (MSRDC) and is designed under the ‘Engineering, Procurement, and Construction (EPC) model. It is bestowed to provide enhanced connectivity to the Marathwada and Vidharbha regions. It is an ambitious project worth Rs. 55, 322crore. Which needed nearly 8,861-hectare land of 24,000 farmers across 10 districts. It is one of the biggest land acquisitions of its kind since the new land Act in 2013 came into force. The state managed to acquire land required for the project in 18 months. The land acquired as per the Right to Fair Compensation and Transparency in Land Acquisition, Rehabilitation and Resettlement Act, 2013 (RFCTLARR) by providing proper compensation to the affected families. The compensation would be given as per the Entitlement Matrix developed, approved and adopted said act.

II. RESEARCH PROBLEM

The Maharashtra government has undertaken the construction of a 701 km long road connecting the two capital cities Mumbai and Nagpur. It aimed at creating a fast and easy public transport chain. The government has set up a special cell to acquire the land required for this highway. This highway passes through 15 villages in Vaijapur taluka which is a drought prone area. Therefore, the economic condition of the farmers here is normal. Prior to the acquisition, the farmers had just enough income to meet the daily needs. So they had very little surplus money and hence they led a miserable life for decades. They failed to start other ventures due to the poor financial situation. They had been under debt as well.

Amidst this, the government of Maharashtra acquired 450 hectares of land spread across 15 villages by paying four times the market price and this made them rich overnight. This gave rise to a big sociological problem: They lacked proper financial management skills: some got addicted too. The way they utilize this fund makes an important study from socio-economic point of view. It is necessary to study how they utilize their money.

So to do the study of social and economic changes that have taken place in the lives of affected farmers. From the 15 villages, we have selected 05 villages for the present study because they are ones that had the large highway length. The length of this highway through the five villages of Vaijapur Tehsil is about 14.8 km.

A. Objective of the project

- To study the Socio-economic impact of Samruddhi Mahamarg on beneficiary families.
- To understand the attitudes of beneficiaries about Samruddhi Mahamarg.
- To study the patterns of social change in Samruddhi Mahamarg affected villages.

B. Hypothesis

- The economically remunerated farmers have developed their farms.
- The farmers who have received financial compensation have started new business.
- Addiction is on the rise among economically remunerated farmers.
- Dispute have arisen among family members over the distribution of compensation.

III. REVIEW OF LITERATURE

- Nhung Pham Thi, Martin Kappas and Daniel Wyss (2020)¹ carried out a case study about the impact of agricultural land acquisition for urbanization on gender equality in affected household at Vietnam. In this article they noted that, Project have improved the infrastructure, created non-farming job opportunities and have begun to change the gender ideology. In this context, women's economic position in affected communes has improved and their employment has switched to non-agriculture activities, which has created a higher income for them. As, a result, their income contribution and their savings have increased.
- T. Chandy, R. Keenan, R. Petheram and P. Shepherd (2012)² studied the impact of hydroelectricity projects on livelihood of rural people in Sikkam. In this article they opined that the construction of hydroelectricity projects caused deforestation and damage to trees, in and around the villages, destroyed by construction work. It has reduced agricultural productivity. It has change in their occupation from farming to non-farming employment. Employment of villagers in hydroelectricity projects decline in social networking that existed in the form of cooperative sharing labour for agriculture. The informal village –level networks to meet exigencies such as food or fuel shortage were losing importance. This loss of social capital had greater impacts on small-and medium-scale farmers.
- Centre for Marketing Research and Social Development Pvt. Ltd. (2018)³ carried out a study about social impact of Land Acquisition for Construction of Khurda Road Bypass line between Argul and Haripurgram of Puri District. Acquisition of 1.61 acres of private land in Godiput Matiapada village under Deland tehsil of Puri district. Survey was undertaken in affected village involving 50 project affected families. The social benefits of the project reveal that, highest 84.78% (39) opined that the project will create easy communication facilities to the local people. In case of economic benefits 80.43% (37) opined for high rate of property value in the locality does to construction of Khurda road by-pass line.

1. Nhung Pham Thi, Martin Kappas and Daniel Wyss (2020)¹Benefits and Constraints of the Agricultural Land Acquisition for Urbanization for Household Gender Equality in Affected Rural Communes: A Case Study in Huong Thuy Town, Thua Thien Hue Province, Vietnam, Land2020, 9, 249; doi:10.3390/

2. T. Chandy, R. Keenan, R. Petheram and P. Shepherd (2012)², Impacts of Hydropower Development on Rural Livelihood Sustainability in Sikkam, India: Community Perceptions, Mountain Research and Development vol. 32 Issue 2 May 2012

³ Social Impact Assessment Study of Land Acquisition for Construction of Khurda Road Bypass line between Argul and Haripurgram of Puri District, Centre for Marketing Research and Social Development Pvt. Ltd. (2018) Available at <https://puri.nic.in/> visited on 22/01/2022

- T. T. NGUYEN et al. (2019)⁴ studied the Effect of Land Acquisition (1191 km²) and Compensation on the Livelihoods of people in Quang Ninh District of Vietnam. The article investigates the impact of land acquisition and compensation on the employment and income of people whose land was acquired for the construction of an industrial park Projects Quang Ninh District, Quang Binh Province. The result indicates, land acquisition leads to a shortage of productive land, labour surplus and unstable income. The household income from agriculture after land acquisition decreased significantly by 27.3% because 70% of households used the money for construction and renovation of houses and shopping purpose. Limited farmers were successful in reconstructing their livelihoods. Much of the compensation received was invested in housing and family furniture, while little was spent on income- generating activities.
- Nyandaro Mteki et. al. (2017)⁵ studied the social impacts induced by an airport expansion project in Tanzania. The focus of this analysis was to assess the resettlement's impact on sources of income and the availability of employment opportunities. Significant loss of employment was observed in jobs such as food and drink vendors and self-entrepreneurial work. The inadequate provision of social services, loss of income sources, and lack of employment opportunities in the new settlement are contributed to their high levels of dissatisfaction. This was exacerbated by the family separation that resulted from the relocation.
- Maitreesh Ghatak et al. (2011) noted in their working paper, "Land acquisition reduced incomes of owner cultivator and tenant households, and agricultural workers were more adversely affected than non-agricultural workers."⁶
- Gautam Buddha University (2021)⁷ because of airport, boost to good road connectivity with larger markets and major trade centre's the 75 % project affected peoples believed that this increased mobility and connectivity will provide them with formal and informal business opportunities and increase in employment productivity.

IV. RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

The following section provides the methodology adopted for undertaking the baseline data collection and impact assessment of the project.

A. Research Site:

The 'Mumbai-Nagpur Super Communication Expressway' officially known as 'Hindu Hrudaysamarat Balasaheb Thackeray Maharashtra Samruddhi Mahamarg,' (HHBTMSM). It is the country's largest Greenfield roadway project in Maharashtra connecting the two capitals of the state i.e., Mumbai and Nagpur. It traverse through 10 key districts directly and indirectly 14 districts (24 Talukas, and 392 villages) via feeder roads. It would reduce the travel time between Mumbai and Nagpur by 8 hours (Eight hours instead of 16). It is bestowed to provide enhanced connectivity to the Marathwada and Vidharbha regions.

B. Literature and Method

The present paper is based on (survey method) quantitative approach. A self-administered questionnaire has been developed & used as an instrument of data collection. Out of the 15 villages affected by the Samrudhi expressway in Vaijapur taluka, the first five villages were selected for the study. The data has been collected from 140 respondents of said villages on how they spent the money received. The judgmental or purposive sampling has been used for selection of respondents. To identify the social impact of a project different methods like household interview, focus group discussion, and participative rural appraisal were used to collect responses from the affected people. In which we were used an individual stakeholders to collect the information regarding the social impact of proposed project.

C. Variables

The present research studies the casual relationship between independent and dependent variables. Here education, occupation, nature of house and affected land size are independent variables whereas, construction of house, purchase of new farm, purchase of commercial property, installation new occupation, and modernization of agriculture and consequent family dispute and growing addiction are considered as the dependent variables.

⁴ Truan Tuan Nguyen , G. Hegedus and T. L. Nguyen, Effect of Land Acquisition and Compensation on the Livelihood of People in Quang Ninh District, Quang Binh Province: Labor and Income, Land 2019, 8, 91.

WWW.mdpi.com/journal/land

⁵ Nyandaro Mteki, T. Murayama &S. Nishikizawa, Social Impacts induced by a development project in Tanzania: a case of airport expansion, Impact Assessment and Project Appraisal, (2017)35:2, 272-283.

⁶ Maitreesh Ghatak, Sandip Mitra and Dilip Mookherjee, Land Acquisition for Business and Compensation of Displaced Farmers, International Growth Centre, October 2011, policy brief 3023, www.theigc.org

⁷ Social Impact Assessment Study, Noida International Airport Jewar, Gautam Budh Nagar, Uttar Pradesh, Gautam Buddha University (2021), www.gbu.ac.in

Village	Area in Hector	Lenght road in KM	No. of Affected Farmers	No. of Respondents
Lasur	43.61	3.89	88	27
Ghaigaon	53.00	4.46	80	30
Janbargaon	50.00	3.87	65	23
Dawala	35.67	2.71	85	35
Surala	40.39	3.46	89	25
Total	222	18.39	407	140

Table 1: List of Selected Villages, affected farmers and Respondents

Source: field survey

The above table no.1 shows village wise affected area in hector and number of affected farmers in selected villages. The data that shows 53 hectors of land belonging to 80 respondents has been affected at Ghaigaon. 50 hectors of land belonging to 65 respondents has been affected at

Jambargaon. 43.61 hectors of land belonging to 88 respondents has been affected at Lasur. 40.39 hectors of land belonging to 89 respondents has been affected at Surala and 35.67 hectors of 85 respondents has been affected at Dawala.

Sr. No.	Characteristics	Frequency	Percentage
	Male	135	96.4
	Female	05	3.6
	Total	140	100.00

Table no. 2: Head of Family

Source: field survey

This sample covers 140 respondents. The analysis shows that there is significant variation in respect of this variable. The table illustrates that the majority of them 135 (96.4%) were male and 3 (3.6%) were female.

Sr. No.	Characteristics	Frequency	Percentage	
1	Education	Primary	45	32.1
		Secondary	55	39.3
		higher secondary	27	19.3
		UG	13	9.3
2.	Source of Income	Farming	120	85.7
		Service	8	5.7
		Occupation	12	8.6
3	Category:	OPEN	108	77.1
		SC	29	20.7
		ST	01	0.71
		OBC	01	0.71
		NT	01	0.71
4	Religion	Hindu	101	72.1
		Islam	09	6.4
		Buddhist	29	20.7
		Jain	01	0.7
5	Nature of House	Slab	94	67.9
		Tin	43	30.7
		Hut	3	2.4

Table 3: Distribution of the Male respondents in terms of their education, occupation, and caste category, religion and nature of house

Source: field survey

This table 3 highlights the composition of respondents in terms education, occupation caste and religion. The analysis of respondent's characteristics is based on the field work. Education is one of the achievements of the respondent. It has an impact on their personality, decision making power, employment etc. With regard to education, it is clear that out of the 140 respondents 55 (39.3%) have

obtained secondary level education. Out of 140 respondents, 45 (32.1%) have obtained primary level education. 19.3 per cent have completed their higher secondary education. 9.3 per cent respondents have obtained their graduation.

Occupation gives human beings many benefits like money status, gratification etc. Here, majority 140 (85.7%) respondents are engaged in agricultural activity. 5.7% are service holders. 8.6% pursue some kind of occupations. The data also indicates that the maximum rural population depends on agriculture for their livelihood.

Caste plays a role in rural social structure. It affects individual social behaviour and the social order in rural unity. With regard to caste, it is clear that out of 140 respondents 108 (77.1%) belong to open (Maratha) caste. Out of 140 respondents, 29 (20.7) belong to Scheduled Caste category. 01 respondent belongs to ST and NT category each.

Religion and its associated aspects influence rural society. In the countryside caste and religion are inseparable factors. Caste emanates from religion. There are basic six religions viz. Hindu, Islam, Buddhist, Jain, Shikh and Christianity found in Indian Society. Here, in this analysis, out of 140 respondents 101 (72.1) are Hindu, 20.7% are Buddhist, 09 (6.4) are Muslim (Islam) and 01 belongs to Jain community.

Housing is a fundamental human need. It provides security, control, a sense of belonging, identity, and privacy. It is not only a mere physical structure but also a symbol of power, authority and a host of other things that come along with it. With regard to the type of housing, the data shows that of 140 respondents 67.9% live in Pakka (cement concrete) houses while 30.7% live in Kaccha (tin) house and 2.4% live in huts.

Sr. No.	Characteristics	Frequency	Percentage
	Build House	89	63.6
	Purchase a Vehicle	82	58.6
	Loan repayment.	32	22.9
	Purchase a house	20	14.3
	Professional shops	27	19.3
	purchase of home appliances	27	19.3
	Total	140	100.00

Table 4: Expenditure Profile of Respondents

Source: field survey

Table no.4 indicates the way the money earned from the acquisition is utilized by farmers. Out of 140 respondents 89 (63.6%) have build their house. 58.6% have purchased a vehicles. 35.00% said they have purchased gold and 22.9% have paid their indebt. 31.4 per cent purchase a plot in city.19.3% have purchased professional shops in cities. 14.3% have purchased new houses in cities. 19.3% purchased a useful home appliances. **“Madhukar Pande, 48, a farmer from Kacchigatti village in Jalna, who surrendered 1.5 acre out of his 4-acre ancestral agriculture land for the project. The MSRDC paid him Rs 31 lakh per acre. “his annual income from farming was just around Rs 3-5 lakh a year; sufficient enough for sustenance but not enough to save big for the future but, when he getting a compensation he has bought a 4,000 sq ft plot in an adjoining village and constructed a three-storey building which he has rented out as shops and residences. “It is already fetching him a rent of Rs 17,000 a month.” He reinvested a sum in buying farm land near the highway, build a pucca house for himself and setting aside some for his daughter who is a Class 12 student.”⁸**

⁸ <https://indianexpress.com/article>

Sr. No.	Characteristics	Frequency	Percentage
	Gold Purchase	49	35
	Plot purchase	44	31.4
	fixed deposit	118	84.3
	Investment in land	62	44.3
	investment in life insurance	44	31.4
	Total	140	100.00

Table 5: Investment Provisions have made for meeting future rising expenditure

Source: Field survey

Private property gives individuals opportunity to earn, invest, and accumulate wealth. That accumulation can be used for future consumption as well. Human needs are inherently infinite and private property helps to accumulate wealth and satisfy future wants.

35.00% said they have purchased a gold. 31.4% purchased land plots in city. Out of 140 respondents, 118 (84.3%) have preferred fix deposit. 44.3% respondents have invested in land for future use. 31.4% respondents said they have invested in life insurance. **Ashok Chakdhare, 52, says farmers often hesitate due to emotional attachment to the land. He said, “Arid or otherwise, farmers do not really want to give up land. But the compensation being offered was too good to refuse.” Chakdhare surrendered 5 acres of his land in Amravati’s Nimhangaon village and was given a compensation of Rs 1 crore for it. He has reinvested this money into 4 acres of orange orchard, built pucca houses for himself and parents and continues farming in the land he has retained.”⁹**

⁹ <http://timesofindia.indiatimes.com/articleshow>

Sr. No.	Characteristics	Frequency	Percentage
	going to daily wages close	16	11.4
	stop in doing own agriculture	4	2.9
	use a labour for agriculture	78	55.7
	Increases in addiction	41	29.28
	increases in laziness	79	56.42
	increase in expenditure	108	77.14
	none of above	42	30
	Total	140	100.00

Table 6: Compensation Impact on behaviour of affected farmers

Source: Field survey

The table no.6 indicates changing behaviour of respondents after receiving the compensation money of Samruddhi Express Highway. Out of 140, 55.7% respondents have started getting the agricultural work done by employing wagers. They have stopped doing the agricultural work for themselves. Also 11.4% said they

stopped working in other farms on daily wages. 30.00% said that there was no change in their routine life after they received the money. 77.14% respondents said their expenditure has increased. 56.42% said that they have become lazy. 29.28% said that they have developed addiction.

Sr. No.	Characteristics	Frequency	Percentage
	Tube / bore well	61	43.6
	Pipe line	89	63.6
	making agro pond	17	12.1
	Buying couple of bullock	3	2.1
	Purchase a cow's / buffaloes	16	11.4
	Total	140	100.00

Table 7: Investment of Land Development

Source: Field survey

Table no.7 indicates the investment made in the development of agriculture. Out of 140 respondents 89 (63.6%) said that they have strengthened the irrigation by

laying pipeline. 43.6 per cent said they do the tube well and bore well. 12.1% have created small lakes or reservoirs in their farm.

Sr. No.	Characteristics	Frequency	Percentage
1	Increases demand of money by relatives	45	32.1
2	Conflict between brethren	48	34.3
3	Changes in a nature of neighbourhood	58	41.4
4	Demanding a money by sister.	12	8.6
	Total	140	100.00

Table 8: Impact on Social relation

Source: Field survey

Table no.8 shows the experience of farmers after getting a money. 41.4 per cent respondents said they have experienced in changing nature and behaviour of their neighbours. 34.3% said that the money has caused conflict between brothers over the distribution of compensatory money. 32.1% said their relatives are demanding a money. 8.6% said their sisters are demanding money even after their marriage.

V. FINDINGS

- The total 222 hectares area is affected by Samruddhi Express Highway across five villages.
- Total 407 families are affected by Samruddhi Express Highway in five villages.
- The 140 respondents, 106.31 acres of land are affected by Samruddhi Express Highway.

- Out of 140 respondents 28 families are disputed regarding Money distribution
- 13 families have submitted disputes in the court over the distribution of the compensatory money.
- Out of the 140 respondents, 55 (39.3%) have secondary and 45 (32.1) per cent have only primary level education.
- The 85.7% respondents are still engaged in agriculture activity.
- The 108 (77.1%) belong to (Maratha) caste (Open category) and 29 (20.7%) belong to SC category.
- The 101 (72.1%) respondents belong to Hindu religion.
- 67.9% live in Pakka (cement concrete) house. 30.7% belong Kaccha (Tinn) house and only 2.4 per cent live in huts.
- Out of 140 respondents 11 have become landless.
- The 63 (45%) have purchased new land.
- 89 (63.6) per cent have constructed their house.

- Out of 140 respondents 75 (53.6%) have purchase a commercial property in city.
- 100% respondents said the average price of land has increased in all Samruddhi Expressway affected villages because some farmers have started purchasing additional land.
- Out of 140 affected respondents 24 have started a new occupations.
- The 69.3% respondents said their unproductive expenses has increased.
- 118 (84.3%) have done fix deposit in the bank.
- 55.7% respondents have started outsourcing their agricultural work by employing labour.
- The 62 (44.3%) have purchased two wheeler and 25.7% have purchased four wheelers.

VI. DISCUSSION AND SUMMARY

Acquisition of land by a project usually causes loss of land and displacement of habitations warranting rehabilitation of people. But in the present case, the project does not cause dislocation of habitations leading to rehabilitation of people. The Vaijapur taluka is a drought prone area. Therefore, the economic condition of the farmers here is normal. So, they could not start other businesses or ventures because they did not have enough money. They could make both ends meet in the past. But now they could start new business as they have received money. For example, 'Dnyaneshwar Digambar Kolte of Tuljapur village in Maharashtra's Aurangabad district has got Rs 23.4 crore, from the state government for surrendering 9.5 acres out of their 16-acre ancestral land for the Mumbai-Nagpur Samruddhi Expressway.'¹⁰ The farmers in Ghaigaon and Jambargaon, after having received the money, opened restaurants on the state highway. Along with this, the poultry business also flourished. Some people have become self-employment by opening restaurants, grocery shops while others have bought commercial vehicle like trucks, Lorries, JCBs, tractors, pickup vans, goods carriers etc. Many famers utilized the money for developing their land by digging wells, bore wells, constructing new farms lakes, laying pipelines etc. Large reservoirs have been created at the site excavated for secondary minerals along the Samrudhi expressway.

Some farmers have built bungalows which have modern facilities and amenities and have automobiles in their garage. The business of hoteliers in and around the city is booming. Some of them visit the highway restaurants regularly and pay the bills on monthly basis. The farmers have purchased kitchen gadgets like freezers, mixers, cookers, etc. They also have craze for gold ornaments and gold jewellery. They make the wedding functions of their wards more glittering and expensive. Young people have Android phones. Farmers who have no land left in the villages have migrated to big town and cities and settled there for good.

Similarly, people are fighting over the distribution of the money. The economically vulnerable people have become financially stable and that's why they now started to be equal to the few rich people and this is an important social change. This newly rising rich people in the village has started to lead the village in political matters. The taluka and districts level political (MP'S and MLA'S) leaders have tapped their power in the field of politics. This new political group has started to challenge the old leadership. Some of them also bought land out of the compensatory money at other villages at the initiation of their relatives.

VII. CONCLUSION

The farmers have become self-employment by opening restaurants, on the state highway, the poultry business, grocery shops while others have bought commercial vehicle like trucks, Lorries, JCBs, tractors, pickup vans, goods carriers etc. Many famers utilized the money for developing their land by digging wells, bore wells, constructing new farms lakes, laying pipelines etc. and some have bought bullock too. Large reservoirs have been created at the site excavated for secondary minerals along the Samrudhi expressway.

Those who have compensation received for agricultural land, most of them the money was spent on building houses and buying vehicles. Out of the remaining amount, people have spent on gold, farm purchases and modernization of agriculture. 84.37% people have invested money in fix deposit scheme. Due to the sudden arrival of money, some people in the village hate him and some people are consciously trying to get closer to him. With the sudden arrival of money, people's daily expenses, laziness and addiction have increased. There was a slight increase in the addiction level in these villages. Similarly, people are fighting over the distribution of the money. The Samrudhi expressway has caused a great deal of damage to the environment due to the extraction of secondary minerals in the area. It has a protective wall on both sides has hampered the free movement of wildlife. There is a problem of road for farmers coming and going on both sides of the road. The established rich people could manage the money properly, but those who suddenly got rich failed to manage the money and become bankrupt in a few months or years. The dry land located in drought prone village has now become valuable.

The Mumbai-Nagpur Expressway is six lane road. It has a protective wall, so animals and footers will not be a hindrance to vehicle. This highway can be driven at a maximum speed of 120 km ph. The 17 housing projects will be set up on this highway. Special space has also been set up for CCTV cameras and free telephone booths at five KM each, Optical Fibre Cable and special space for Gas Pipeline and power line has also been set up. This highway connects to Delhi-Mumbai Industrial Corridor, Western Dedicated Freight Corridor, Wardha and Jalna Dry Port and Jawaharlal Nehru Port Trust in Mumbai. The Maharashtra government has envisages driving massive employment opportunities to people from their primitive occupation i.e., Agriculture or agro-related businesses, increase manufacturing & industrial potential, better commuting experience, and migration

¹⁰ <https://www.moneycontrol.com/news, Dec.11.2020>.

control through this Mahamarg. It is conducive to development of agro-processing & allied businesses and Tourism. If the project is completed, it would contribute in economy development, fast transportation, reducing road accidents, improving quality of life of the people/users by providing better, quick and safe commuting. So it has beneficial to industrial development of Vidharbha and Marathwada region.

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